

Warping Torsion in Sandwich Panels: A Numerical Parametric Study Regarding the Rotation and Stress Distribution

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ABSTRACT

In new lightweight façade applications, sandwich panels are subjected to eccentric loads alongside conventional bending loads, particularly evident in sandwich panels equipped with supplementary curtain walls or photovoltaic modules. Existing calculation models for eccentrically loaded sandwich panels primarily rely on Saint-Venant's torsion theory. Nonetheless, recent research has unveiled torsion-induced normal stresses in both face sheets, indicating the necessity to consider additional mechanical effects such as warping torsion. Building upon an experimentally validated finite element model in ANSYS, an extensive parameter study was conducted, varying geometric and material-related properties, to perform detailed analyses of the structural response of the sandwich panel under torsion. In this paper the key findings of this study are presented and discussed concerning the rotation and stress distribution plotted against the identified main parameters.

Keywords: sandwich panels, warping torsion, numerical parameter study, structural response

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation and Objective

Sandwich panels, consisting of two thin steel face sheets with a thick shear-deformable low-density polyisocyanurate (PU) or mineral wool core in between, have proven as cost-effective building envelopes, especially in the European industrial sector. These prefabricated lightweight components offer excellent thermal insulation and sealing performance at the same time. Recent advancements involve subjecting sandwich wall panels to additional eccentric loads, particularly those equipped with photovoltaic, or curtain wall modules fastened on the exterior face sheets via rails (1; 2). In these applications, sandwich panels experience torsional loads due to the additional and eccentrically acting module weight. Previous analytical calculation models, relying on Saint-Venant's torsion theory, are being reconsidered due to the latest findings indicating torsion-induced normal stresses in the top and bottom face sheets.

For this purpose, a research project has been initiated at TU Darmstadt with the aim of developing a new calculation approach to describe the structural behaviour of eccentrically loaded sandwich panels. To achieve this objective, ongoing efforts involve experimental, numerical, and analytical studies. In this context, the general applicability of warping torsion has already been confirmed by experimental, numerical, and analytical results obtained for eccentric point loads perpendicular to the sandwich plane, acknowledging the limitations of this approach. The detailed results are given in (3). In the present paper, the main results from recent extended numerical parameter studies on single-span PU sandwich panels subjected to a uniformly distributed torsional load are showcased. Here, a broader range of geometry and material-related parameters are incorporated, emphasising the rotation and normal and shear stress of the analysed sandwich panels.

1.2 State of the Art

The research on torsion in sandwich structures dates back to the mid-1950s and remains relevant today. Initially, Seide (4) and Cheng (5) derived torsional stiffness formulas for rectangular sandwich plates based on Saint-Venant's theory. In 1974, Stamm and Witte (6) introduced a more practical calculation model following the methodology to determine the torsional stiffness of thin-walled, closed cross-sections, treating the core as infinitesimal vertical lamellae. The significance of torsion grew in the 1980s with the widespread use of sandwich panels in building envelopes. During this period, Höglund (7) formulated a torsional stiffness formula based on the Bredt formula, neglecting 1/3 of the inner core area, for sandwich panels with window openings. For this application, it results in an eccentric load to the adjacent panel connected through a joint, which, in return, can lead to a torsional stress.

In the 2010s, Rädcl (8) questioned those theories, revealing torsion-induced normal stresses from torsional loads in panels with openings, contrary to prior calculation models and obtaining significantly higher torsional stiffnesses from experiments than calculated by those. In this context, numerical studies for sandwich panels with openings verified this experimental finding in principle. Pozorski and Wojciechowski (9) addressed this issue by considering warping torsion in their analytical approach and focusing on different idealized boundary conditions and loadings in their numerical model. In 2022, Wurf et al. (10) developed a model based on extended high-order sandwich panel theory, accounting local effects resulting from the soft core, comparing it to the approach of (9) and their numerical model. As with the latter references, current research into the load-bearing behaviour of sandwich panels in building construction under eccentric loading is increasingly demonstrating that numerical simulation are an appropriate and efficient approach (11; 12). Further insights of literature on eccentrically loaded sandwich panels are given in (3).

Despite these advances, the current European standard for sandwich panels EN 14509:2013 (13) does not address torsion, encouraging ongoing efforts to develop recommendations for the calculation methods for future standards.

1.3 Fundamentals

While sandwich panels appear like plates, they are nonetheless treated as beams for bending loads, for example, from wind or temperature. Here, the European standard EN 14509:2013 provides practical calculation formulas for stiffness, deformations, and stresses. This simplification is extended to the case of torsion in this paper. The term "torsion" is used analogously to beams when discussing "eccentrically loaded" sandwich panels.

Torsion in a beam is present when rotations, represented as $\vartheta(x)$, manifest around its longitudinal axis x , and additionally these rotations vary along its length ($\vartheta'(x) > 0$). Generally, torsion can be categorized into Saint-Venant's torsion, where solely shear stresses τ_{xy} are present, and warping torsion, which additionally involves normal stresses σ_w . In structural engineering, the analysis typically assumes the Bernoulli and Wagner hypotheses. Moreover, in the case of Saint-Venant's torsion, it is assumed that warping occurs free. The general differential equation for torsion is well-established and can be expressed by the relationship between torsional moment $m_T(x)$ and the derivatives of the beams rotation, while introducing the decay factor λ , as shown in *Eq. (1)*. Numerous solutions for the differential equation, considering various boundary conditions and load applications, are available in the literature (14).

$$\frac{m_T(x)}{EI_w} = -\lambda^2 \vartheta''(x) + \vartheta''''(x) \quad \text{with} \quad \lambda = \sqrt{\frac{GI_T}{EI_w}} \quad (1)$$

The required torsional stiffnesses for the sandwich panel can be calculated for the Saint-Venant components with the formulas introduced by Stamm and Witte, see *Eq. (2)*.

$$GI_T = 4 G_F e^2 b \frac{t_1 t_2}{t_1 + t_2} \left(1 - \frac{\tanh(\Omega b/2)}{\Omega b/2} \right) \quad \text{with} \quad \Omega = \frac{G_{xz,C}}{G_F} \frac{t_1 + t_2}{d_C \cdot t_1 t_2} \quad (2)$$

By considering the warping stiffness based on an analogy to I-beams, Eq. (3) is derived.

$$EI_W = \frac{E_F b^3}{12} (e_1^2 t_1 + e_2^2 t_2) \quad (3)$$

Given the emphasis on the numerical approach in this paper, the static system, depicted in Fig. 1, was analysed for the simplified cases, “both sided fork supported” ($k_w \rightarrow 0, k_{d,x} \rightarrow \infty$) and “both sided clamped” ($k_w \rightarrow \infty, k_{d,x} \rightarrow \infty$), solely as a reference. The calculation formulas for the stresses in the face sheets and the core of the sandwich panels subjected to warping torsion are provided in (3).

Fig. 1. Static system of a single span beam subjected to a uniformly distributed torsional moment m_T .

2 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS METHOD BACKGROUND

2.1 General

To understand the structural behaviour of eccentrically loaded sandwich panels, comprehensive studies are required, encompassing experimental, analytical and numerical methods. Experiments are essential for validating models and providing reality checks, particularly when evaluating components like sandwich panels with manufacture-dependent and strongly scattering material properties. However, tests are often elaborate, and the scope of parameters and measurements is usually limited. In such cases, numerical simulations prove beneficial for expanding parameter scopes and enable detailed investigations. Another advantage is that individual parameters can be deliberately varied and are not dependent on the properties of the available test specimens. For this purpose, an extensive parametric study, grounded in an experimental validated numerical model aims primarily to identify relationships between the structural response and the panels properties. In Fig. 2, the geometry and the loading of the sandwich panels are depicted schematically, introducing the points of interest (POI) for subsequent data analysis on rotation, normal and shear stress.

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of the sandwich panel, including the loading¹ $h = m_T / (e \cdot b)$ and the points of interest.

¹ The horizontal load h was drawn intentionally with an offset to the face sheet planes for reasons of clarity. In the numerical simulations, it acts in the plane of the face sheets, respectively.

2.2 Implementation of the Parametric Reference Model

2.2.1 Finite elements, materials, mesh

For the numerical investigation, a parametric 3D finite element model was developed in ANSYS Workbench 2022 R2 (15), as illustrated in *Fig. 3*. In this model, the face sheets were idealized as plane surfaces using 4-noded linear shell elements (SHELL281), while the core was modelled with 8-noded linear solid elements (SOLID185). Similar solid elements were employed for the bearing structure in general. The steel face sheets of the sandwich panel and the other steel components were characterized using an isotropic linear elastic material model with $E_F = 210,000$ MPa and $\mu_F = 0.3$. The PU rigid foam core of the sandwich panel was defined as an anisotropic linear elastic material with shear and Young's moduli set equally in all directions, unless otherwise noted, and a Poisson's ratio μ_C of 0.25. The detailed values of the parametrized dimensions and material properties differ for the validation and the parameter study and are given therefore in the respective sections 2.3 and 2.4.

Fig. 3. Finite element model of a sandwich panel in ANSYS.

Regarding the meshing, the Sweep Method was utilised for the solid elements, with finer meshes in vicinity to discontinuity areas. This approach is also advantageous for controlling the number of elements of the shear-deformable core in the z-direction. The mesh size was specified at 25 mm on average, in accordance with a prior convergence study.

2.2.2 Load application

Three load situations (LS) were initially implemented for the numerical simulation, each applied in a single time step. While in (3) the test-based validation of the numerical model was the main goal, in this paper, the aim is to gain a deeper understanding of the static mechanical relations between internal forces and stresses. Primarily, LS I incorporates, according to the eccentric six-point bending test series, four eccentric acting vertical loads for which the resulting torsional moment was set constant $M_T = m_T \times L = 4 \times F \times e = 3 \text{ kN} \times 0.35 \text{ m} = 1,05 \text{ kNm}$. Secondly, LS II, a superposition of “pure” bending and “pure” torsion loads was introduced, demonstrating that the results from this approach are in accordance with LS I. Here, the “pure” bending part was applied with a uniformly distributed vertical surface load acting on the entire top face sheet. For the torsional part, two opposite-directed horizontal surface loads act in the plane of both face sheets, directing in positive or negative y-direction, respectively. Thirdly, for the parameter study shown in this paper, LS III was considered, where solely the “pure” torsion part applied in which m_T (LS III) was set constant $m_T = 0.25 \text{ kNm/m}$ as depicted schematically in *Fig. 2*.

2.2.3 Contact definition

Preliminary investigations disclosed that the modelling of the bearing structure is one crucial aspect of the implementation. For a holistic approach, the challenge lies in harmonizing the boundary conditions of the experimental, numerical, and analytical characteristics to a required extent.

Initially, the experimental bearing structure was modelled and subsequently modified. The mechanism of the roller bearing was modelled for the cylindrical steel with a general “Body-Ground”

connection, setting the appropriate degrees of freedom concerning translation and rotation. Since the face sheets and core were treated as one component in the ANSYS tool DesignModeler, there was no need to explicitly define contacts within the sandwich panel.

In contrast, asymmetric contact pairs in the top and bottom interfaces of the sandwich panel and the bearing structure were manually defined as CONTA174 and TARGE170 elements, respectively, utilizing the Augmented Lagrange method. In each calculation iteration, these contact elements check whether the corresponding contact partner is penetrated. If this is the case, this penetration is counteracted by a defined contact stiffness that can be compared with the effect of a spring. In several iterations, the penetrations and the resulting restoring forces are then brought into equilibrium with the applied loads until the penetrations become negligibly small and the solution converges. A non-linear contact formulation was necessary due to the fact that the fork support of the test setup based on which this reference model was generated may exhibit clearance due to the compressibility of the panels core and low stiffness in lateral bending. Therefore, preliminary investigations concerning the contact status across the panel width at the supports were conducted.

For both the upper and lower interfaces, two types of non-linear contacts were considered: frictional and rough. The bonded contact type, a linear approach, was ruled out as a suitable choice at an early stage. The various contact types play distinct roles in transferring forces. Bonded contacts facilitate the transfer of compressive, tensile, and shear forces, while non-linear contacts (rough and frictional) omit tensile forces but convey shear and compressive forces. In the case of the frictional type, shear forces are transmitted based on the friction value. When dealing with non-linear contact types, it is recommended to configure the “Large Deflection” setting, considering the influences from second-order theory. For the validation model, a friction value, calibrated to 0.1, accounts for the effective area activated for friction (considering the presence of lined face sheets) and the characteristics of the material surfaces. Here, test setup-specific characteristics can be simulated accurately. For the further numerical parameter study, a rough contact was formulated since the fundamental structural behaviour can hereby been simulated in the same manner as for the frictional contact type but with moderate computing time. (15)

Fig. 4. Bearing structure detail regarding the contact definition.

2.3 Validation of the Parametric Reference Model

The numerical model was validated for LS I with results of the newly developed eccentric six-point bending test of sandwich panels with varying geometric and material-dependent parameters, as shown in *Table 1*. The newly developed eccentric six-point bending test is based on the single span test-up of EN 14509:2013, Annex A, but with eccentric acting point loads and fork supports. A total of 52 individual tests with 20 unique parameter configurations were conducted, incorporating each nine strain gauges locating on the top and bottom face sheets and four displacement transducers on the bottom face sheet at midspan and approximately quarter span.

Table 1. Parameter of the tested sandwich panels for model validation.

parameter	symbol	parameter range
shear modulus	G_C	3.0 - 4.4 MPa
Young's modulus	E_C	3.3 - 5.0 MPa
core thickness	D	40 - 220 mm
total width	B	900 mm
total length	L	4000 - 6000 mm
sheet thickness	t_1, t_2	0.40 - 0.63 mm
total load	F	3 kN

Fig. 5 exemplifies the test-based validation of the numerical model. The diagram presents the results of the numerical model with LS I and LS II alongside the experimental data. It illustrates the qualitative distribution of the normal stress (primary y-axis, on the left side) and the vertical displacement (secondary y-axis, on the right side) across the panel width at midspan for a tested sandwich panel with $D = 160$ mm, $L = 5000$ mm, $b = 900$ mm, $t_1 = 0.63$ mm, and $t_2 = 0.5$ mm at $F = 3$ kN. The close alignment of both approaches is evident. Deeper insights into the validation, including a correlation analysis of the experimental and numerical approaches across the shown parameter range, are provided in (2).

Fig. 5. Validation of the FE model exemplarily shown through the normal stress and displacement distribution.

2.4 Methods and Scope of the Numerical Parametric Study

Based on the validated parametric numerical model, the scope and range of parameters were significantly extended compared to the experimental study, as outlined in Table 2, while considering the limitations for practical applications. In total, 858 configurations were analysed, applying the torsional loading LS III. Beginning with the reference series, which considers 11 core thicknesses in combination with 6 different lengths each, 12 further series were simulated, varying additional geometry-, material- and load-related parameters. For all configurations the Young's modulus of the core was set to $E_C = 4$ MPa and the Poisson's ratio $\mu_C = 0.25$. For each data series a numerical matrix including in the results in the points of interests, as shown in Fig. 2, was collected from ANSYS for subsequent rotation and stress analysis and data visualization in MATLAB R2022b.

Table 2. Scope of the parameters for the extended numerical parametric study.

#	parameter	symbol	reference series	parameter range
1	core thickness	D	40 - 240 mm	as reference series
2	total length	L	3000 - 8000 mm	as reference series
3	total width	b	900 mm	600 - 1200 mm
4	sheet thickness	t_1, t_2	0.5 mm	0.4 - 0.6 mm
5	core shear modulus (xz)	$G_{C,xz}$	4 MPa	2 - 6 MPa
6	core shear modulus (yz)	$G_{C,yz}$	4 MPa	2 - 6 MPa
7	load level coefficient	f	1	0.5 - 2

3 RESULTS OF THE NUMERICAL PARAMETRIC STUDY

The numerical parametric study provides a diverse portfolio of valuable results for a static-mechanical grounded data analysis. In the following, five diagrams are showcased to provide data-driven evidence of relationships between the analysed parameters and the resultant magnitudes at the respective points of interest. For the visualization of the numerical results 2D scatter plots were generated, while for the normal stress, additionally a 3D scatter plot was employed (Fig. 6–8). In general, the plots incorporate the 13 series, with each consisting of 66 data points. The individual series can be distinguished from the reference series by means of the parameters listed in the legend. The fitted analytical results based on the same input parameters were supplemented to contextualize the numerical results. The vertical axis represents the normalized structural responses $\bar{\vartheta}$, $\bar{\tau}_{C,xz}$, $\bar{\tau}_{F,xy}$, $\bar{\sigma}_x$ at the respective points of interest, normalized with the load level coefficient $f = m_T / m_{T,ref}$. The horizontal axis denotes the identified key parameter ratios.

In Fig. 6, the normalized rotation at POI 1 is shown. It is evident that all data points align in a hyperbolic relation between the ratio $D/L^2 \cdot b^3 \sqrt{G_{C,xz} \cdot G_{C,yz}}$ and the rotation. Comparing with the analytical curves the numerical data points matches to the calculated case of $k_w \rightarrow 0$ (red).

Fig. 6. Normalized rotation of the sandwich panel at POI 1.

In Fig. 7, the normalized shear stresses in the core at POI 2 (a) and in the face sheet at POI 3 (b) are illustrated. Once more, it can be observed that all data points align in a hyperbolic relation between the parameter ratio and the respective magnitude. For the shear stress in the core (Fig. 7a) the ratio is $D \cdot b^2 / (L^2 \cdot \sqrt[3]{G_{C,xz}})$. Here, a comparison with the analytical curves reveals that the numerical data points closely match the two analytical approaches, as they are practically congruent. However, the situation is different for the shear stress in the face sheet (Fig. 7b). Plotting the resulting values against the ratio $D/L \cdot b \cdot t_1^2 / t_2 \cdot \sqrt[3]{G_{C,xz}}$ reveals a hyperbolic relationship as described, but the points are slightly more scattered than in the previously discussed graphs. In this case, the curves of the analytical approaches differ, whereby the numerical points are more consistent with the case considering warping constraint $k_w \rightarrow \infty$.

In Fig. 8, the normalized normal stresses in the face sheets at POI 1 are presented. Unlike the previous variables, the results are initially shown in Fig. 8a solely for a selected data set. This is because there is a more complex relationship between the input variables and the normal stress than in the previous cases. Nevertheless, in Fig. 8a, a relationship was found for the ratio $D \cdot t_1 / (L^4 \cdot t_2 \cdot G_{C,yz})$. Obviously, the numerical data points align more to the blue curve for the analytical approach of $k_w \rightarrow \infty$, observing particularly for low x-values a higher scattering. Subsequently, all 13 data series were included in Fig. 8b, introducing a third dimension with the y-axis set to the ratio $b \cdot \sqrt[3]{G_{C,xz}}$

while keeping the other axis the same as in Fig. 8a. As reference, only the analytical approach of case $k_w \rightarrow \infty$ was depicted due to the prior clear classification. Although a basic agreement between the shape of the numerical point cloud and the surface from the fitted analytical results is recognizable, deviations should be acknowledged.

Fig. 7. Normalized shear stress: a) in the core at POI 2; b) in the face sheet at POI 3.

Fig. 8. Normalized normal stress in the face sheet at POI 1: a) 2D Plot; b) 3D Plot.

4 DISCUSSION

In general, a correlation between the input parameter ratios and the resulting rotation and stress values was found, as evident in the presented plots where the point clouds approximately align with curves or surfaces, corresponding to the analytical solutions for the broad parameter selection and ranges. Nevertheless, the unique characteristics are worth discussing briefly, both the actual results from a mechanical point of view but also the methodology behind the data analysis.

For the rotation and the shear stresses in the core and the faces, it appears that the analytical approach without warping constraints $k_w \rightarrow 0$ (red) match more closely to the numerical simulated structural behaviour than the case considering warping constraints $k_w \rightarrow \infty$ (blue), while for the normal stress, it

is clearly the opposite. This may seem contradictory initially. However, it should be acknowledged that only the limit states are covered here through the cases “both sided fork supported” ($k_w \rightarrow 0$, $k_{d,x} \rightarrow \infty$) and “both sided clamped” ($k_w \rightarrow \infty$, $k_{d,x} \rightarrow \infty$). It is conceivable, as previous studies on the eccentric six-point bending test have shown (3), that a more general yet complex analytical calculation considering torsion and warping springs ($k_w > 0$, $k_{d,x} > 0$), as depicted in *Fig. 1*, could lead to a more uniform and aligned result compared to the numerical solution. However, this was neglected here as the focus was on the numerical parametric study. Both the torsion and warping springs enable the mechanical effects of the soft core, accounting the low transverse shear stiffness and the implemented non-linear boundary condition, to be considered to a certain extent.

A closer examination of the scatter of the point clouds from the numerical simulation reveals that the plots of face sheet stresses, particularly the normal stress plot, exhibit notable characteristics. *Fig. 8a* shows high scatter for low x -values. Nevertheless, despite this scatter, the analytical approach covers the envelope curves of the maximum obtained stresses for the respective x -value which could be beneficial for potential engineering calculation models being on the “safe side”. The scattering of the results suggests that there is potential for optimization in the applied parameter ratios. It is worth noting that, for the normal stresses, the analytical data points exhibit scatter, although this aspect was not elaborated in detail in this paper.

For the rotation and both shear stress distributions, a hyperbolic relation was observed. In contrast, for the normal stress distribution, a logarithmic relation was identified, as evident from the applied curve fitting approach. Only for the normal stress distribution, a three-dimensional plot (*Fig. 8b*) was generated, as the data analysis indicate that a multidimensional influence in which the parameters significantly impact the structural response. Particularly, the width and the shear modulus play crucial roles in this regard. This observation supports the theory that there is a transition from a beam-like to a plate-like structural behaviour as the width of the sandwich panel increases. Previous studies (16; 3) have shown that in such cases, a non-linear normal stress distribution across the panel width is obtained, gradually shifting maximum normal stress from the panels edge towards the mid-axis, with the influence of the shear modulus potentially increases accordingly. Furthermore, a trend can be observed wherein deviations from the analytical calculation increase with growing ratio $b \cdot \sqrt[3]{G_{C,xz}}$.

5 CONCLUSION, CONTRIBUTION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, the structural behaviour of PU rigid foam sandwich panels under uniformly distributed torsional loading was analysed through an extensive parametric study. This study was grounded on an experimental validated finite element model in ANSYS and the results were compared to two analytical approaches on warping torsion, with and without warping constraint. To achieve this, a comprehensive data analysis of the structural response was conducted, resulting in scatter plots for each rotation and stress magnitude. The key findings and contributions from this study are summarized as follows:

- *The applicability of warping torsion in single span sandwich panels was confirmed across a broad range of selected geometry-, material- and load-related parameters, encompassing results from a total of 858 configurations.*
- *Key parameter ratios were identified for the rotation, as well as for the shear and normal stresses of the sandwich panel. These ratios resulted in data points from each series forming low scattering curves that generally matched those obtained from the analytical approaches.*
- *In the analysis of normal stress, a significant influence of the width of the sandwich panels on the load-bearing behaviour was identified, supporting the hypothesis of the supplementing consideration of plate effects, and underscoring the importance of a broad parameter range.*
- *The presented scatter plots demonstrate the potential use of nomograms for calculating rotation and stress values of eccentrically loaded sandwich panels for the design of façade applications, acknowledging its limitations in the same way.*

For future research, it is recommended to delve deeper into the influence of the width by considering the sandwich plate theory or secondary shear deformation. This exploration could provide a more comprehensive understanding of the structural behaviour of sandwich panels and the limitations of the application range of warping torsion. Additionally, investigating various load and boundary conditions could enhance the findings and broaden the scope of applicability. Furthermore, in terms of recommendation for the design of eccentrically loaded sandwich panels, the derivation of nomograms or simplified formulas for the rotation and stress calculation could be pursued. These tools could streamline the design process and improve efficiency. Ultimately, the overarching goal should be the development of a simplified approach for designing safe and cost-effective façades.

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